

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION USING MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Jalilova Iroda Alisher's daughter,

*ICT specialist, Department of Preschool Education,
Khojaabad District, Andijan Region*

Abstract: *the content of innovation and innovative activities in the article the essence, the activities of innovative technologies in pre-school education application in the process, to the word "innovation" by foreign and Uzbek scientists given definitions are given. Also, to ""innovation" Innovative activity on", "On Education" and "On Science and Scientific Activity" Laws definitions, relationships given to "Innovation" and "Innovative activity" Opinions on the articles are presented.*

Key words: *Innovation, innovative activity, innovative processes, knowledge economy, digital economy, professional innovative activity.*

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Future in the current period of renewal in Uzbekistan our children who are our descendants, spiritually rich, morally mature, intellectual developed, highly educated and mature in all aspects, unique in his formation as a person is given importance. In this regard, the development of preschool education in our country and a number of regulatory legal documents on effective operation were adopted and comprehensive measures are being implemented.

Including: the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 29, 2016 "2017-Measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2021 on" decision No. PQ-2707 and modern management of preschool education introduction of mechanisms, highly qualified pre-school education organizations filling with specialists and their material and technical equipment and improving the infrastructure, most importantly, the educational process in preschool education In order to improve the system of preschool education on September 9, 2017 Decision No. PQ-3261 "On improvement measures" was adopted done.

Also, on March 19, 2019, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Youth 5 on raising their spirituality and meaningful organization of their free time an important initiative" was put forward. In addition, on May 8, 2019, "Preschool education of the Republic of Uzbekistan Decision No. PQ-4312 on approving the system development concept, No. 391 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 13, 2019 on the activities of preschool educational organizations ada improvement measures on" decision, as well as other regulatory legal documents related to this field serves as the legal basis for reforming the field of preschool education. "In 2017-2021, further improvement of the preschool education system, strengthening of the material and technical base, expansion of the network of preschool education organizations, provision of qualified pedagogic personnel, level of preparation of

children for school education radical improvement, modern educational programs to the educational process and application of technologies, intellectual, moral, aesthetic and intellectual development of children in all aspects preschool education aimed at creating conditions for physical development is of particular importance as an important stage of the fundamental reform of the system. This, in turn, is the introduction of innovative technologies in education, children MTT coverage, regulation of MTT activities and legal basis improvement and qualification of pedagogic personnel and a qualified specialist is serving to provide personnel. Included in preschool practice innovative pedagogical solutions, consistent implementation of diverse and meaningful content It is important to keep track of a number of requirements and projects.

The educational process organized in preschool educational organizations and providing the conditions created in it and innovative education in the system to approach based on technologies should be based on the following factors.

- Individual micro level of innovation (according to some new idea put into practice);
- Micro representing the interaction of individually introduced news level (reciprocity of news introduced separately in this place affected);
- Application of news according to age characteristics and their uniformity in the case far from the level, use of variability.
- Developing children's thinking skills based on new methods.

It follows that pedagogic personnel are qualified specialists in their field if there is personnel, the educational process and quality of preschool education level. This means raising the quality of education to a higher level based on the use of innovative technologies. Innovative education through technologies and methods, development of continuous education system is one of the most important factors. They are subject to certain changes in the educational process, education various initiatives that lead to the enrichment of content, quality and effective organization and appears in the integrated system of news. Educational activities during the educational process successful implementation of the pedagogical process in preschool educational organizations depends on proper organization.

We know that education and upbringing in the pedagogical processes of MTTs are one - It is very important to connect with each other and this is the process of education and training, in practice in everyday life, through work and play is done. Knowledge, skills and abilities that children should acquire It is defined in the state program, which is the general development of children and their is important in preparing for school education. In the process of activities based on the didactic principles of education and upbringing, children are young and unique taking into account its specifics, it is carried out in a certain consistency and gradually becomes more complicated in terms of content.

Comprehensive development of children in preschool educational organizations the pedagogical process aimed at providing is complex, but also very interesting is considered Pre-school education in achieving the effectiveness of education to properly organize each type of activity in organizations, and at the same time from the pedagogue requires high responsibility. A decision embodying common interests and laws, the consistency of the development of the continuous education system in our country and in addition to ensuring its integrity, organizing

the activities of preschool educational organizations applying a creative approach to educational processes, preschool children, improvement of school preparation processes, preschool education organizations formation of the necessary needs and motivations for education in pupils, organization of the activities of children of pre-school educational organizations on a scientific basis and increase the effectiveness of their activities, convenient educational in the educational organization the need to create an environment, that is, to create an innovative educational environment defines.

To demonstrate pedagogical practice in education, preschool educational organizations free and independent thinking skills and spiritual worldview in students formation is not only in specially organized pedagogical processes, but also in their family environment and educational environment, interaction of team members of educational organization the quality of educational relations that arise in the processes of relations and interpersonal relations increases. The educational process organized in preschool educational organizations and the conditions created in it are interrelated, MTTs ensures the stabilization of its activity. Basic education and the conditions created in it, solving various problems that arise in the processes are modern It is carried out using methods, the results are adapted to the requirements of the time and pedagogical system efficiency is ensured. In conclusion, it can be said that innovative approaches to the educational system is the main condition for modernization and achieving educational efficiency.

Construction of pedagogical processes based on innovative approaches in the educational process interesting, active, unconventional, new and innovative in directing students to pleasurable activity it is important to teach them the basics of professional education using methods is the owner.

Rapid development of science and technology, modern information wide implementation of communication systems, rapid knowledge in various fields of science updating, technology and technology changing day by day to get independent education as an opportunity, to create electronic textbooks and develop methods of practical implementation demanding exit.

The content of the electronic textbook created from general professional subjects is education directing the recipients to develop their creative abilities, to receive independent education to create an opportunity, to ensure the formation of skills to search for new knowledge must.

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